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Patterns and drivers of Cladocera community structure in the Black Sea

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Abstract: Cladoceran community dynamics were examined in the Romanian sector of the Black Sea during the warm seasons of 2013–2020, using Marine Reporting Units (MRUs) to evaluate spatial heterogeneity across transitional, coastal, and marine waters. Analyses of density, biomass, mean individual biomass (MIB), and species composition revealed interannual fluctuations superimposed on strong nearshore–offshore gradients, with higher values in transitional and coastal MRUs. The assemblage was consistently dominated by *Pleopsis polyphemoides* and *Penilia avirostris*, which together accounted for most of the total abundance and biomass. Multivariate analysis identified significant differences in taxonomic composition across MRUs and years, while correlation analyses highlighted temperature as the primary environmental driver of cladoceran variability. Nutrient influences were more spatially discrete, reflecting local riverine inputs and hydrodynamic mixing. Shifts in MIB indicated alternations between small- and large-bodied dominance, signaling changes in size structure and potential impacts on pelagic trophic transfer. The high sensitivity of cladocerans to thermal and nutrient regimes underscores their value as indicators for ecosystem assessments under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), particularly within Descriptor 4 (Food Webs) and Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity). The present study provides an improved understanding of cladoceran responses to environmental variability in the northwestern Black Sea and supports their integration into regional monitoring frameworks.

Key words: Coastal–offshore gradient, ecosystem indicators, interannual variability, warm-season plankton

1. Introduction

Cladocerans represent a specialized group of planktonic branchiopods that, although less diverse than copepods, play a disproportionately important role in the pelagic food webs of marine ecosystems (Havel, 2009; Yildiz, 2025). Their short generation times, rapid parthenogenetic reproduction, and high filtration rates allow them to exploit pulses of primary production efficiently, transferring energy from phytoplankton and microbial producers toward planktivorous fish (Degerman et al., 2018; Antón-Pardo et al., 2021; Kotov et al., 2022; Bisinicu and Harcota, 2025; Bisinicu and Lazar, 2025). These traits, together with their sensitivity to changes in temperature, salinity, and food availability, make them effective indicators of environmental variability and ecosystem change (Richardson, 2008).

In marine and brackish systems, cladocerans typically exhibit strong seasonal dynamics, with warm, stratified periods favoring short-lived but dense populations that can alter community structure and trophic coupling. Such

rapid fluctuations in abundance and biomass can modify the balance between herbivory and microbial production, indirectly affecting nutrient recycling and food-web stability. Their strong sensitivity to environmental conditions also means that cladoceran responses often integrate multiple stressors, including warming, altered freshwater inputs, and eutrophication (Adamczuk, 2024; Üstün, 2025).

The Black Sea offers a unique setting for the study of cladoceran dynamics. As a semienclosed basin strongly influenced by the Danube River, it hosts steep ecological gradients, ranging from nearshore, river-influenced waters to marine oligotrophic zones (Ristea et al., 2025). These conditions generate spatial heterogeneity in plankton communities (Bisinicu et al., 2023a; Bisinicu et al., 2023b). Although long-term studies have documented major trends in Black Sea mesozooplankton, research has primarily focused on copepods and gelatinous taxa, with cladocerans usually treated as secondary components of broader community analyses (Stefanova et al., 2012;

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Shiganova and Kazmin, 2024; Anninsky et al., 2025). Studies specifically targeting marine cladocerans remain limited in both spatial and temporal coverage, and those that exist tend to focus on species occurrence rather than quantitative dynamics (Üstün et al., 2018; Üstün, 2025; Yildiz, 2025), leaving interannual variability and coastal–offshore structuring insufficiently resolved. This is particularly notable in the Romanian sector of the Black Sea (Tabarcea, 2017; Bişinicu et al., 2023a; Bişinicu et al., 2024).

Marine Reporting Units (MRUs), as defined under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), provide a useful spatial framework for assessments of such variability, distinguishing between Danube-influenced, coastal, and marine waters (Mihailov et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2016; Bisinicu and Lazar 2024, Bişinicu et al., 2024). This spatially explicit approach is especially relevant for cladocerans, whose populations respond rapidly to hydrographic and trophic changes.

The present study analyses cladoceran dynamics in the Romanian sector of the Black Sea during the warm seasons of 2013–2020 with three main objectives: (1) to quantify interannual and spatial variability in cladoceran density, biomass, and mean individual biomass; (2) to identify the key environmental factors shaping these patterns; and

(3) to examine how spatial and interannual changes in cladoceran abundance, biomass, and size structure reflect the broader pelagic ecosystem conditions in the Black Sea.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study was carried out in the northwestern Black Sea within the territorial waters of Romania (Figure 1). This area has been strongly influenced by the hydrological and biogeochemical effects of the Danube River—the Black Sea’s largest freshwater source. Overall, the region is characterized by environmental gradients resulting from the mixing of nutrient-rich riverine waters with more saline, oligotrophic offshore waters. This leads to steep spatial transitions in salinity, nutrient concentrations, turbidity, and primary productivity, forming a continuum from estuarine-influenced transitional zones to coastal and open-shelf environments (Lazar et al., 2024a, 2024b, 2024c).

To capture this environmental heterogeneity, the analyses were structured according to the MRUs established under the MSFD:

- Danube-influenced transitional waters (T): strongly affected by river discharge, characterized by reduced salinity, elevated nutrient loads, and high productivity;

Figure 1. Study area along the Romanian Black Sea coast showing sampling stations and marine MRUs.

- Coastal waters (C): intermediate conditions with variable terrigenous influence, enhanced phytoplankton biomass, and dynamic hydrography;
- Marine waters (M): offshore, higher-salinity, more stable, and typically oligotrophic regions representing the western Black Sea shelf.

This MRU-based approach facilitates the interpretation of cladoceran spatial patterns in relation to well-defined environmental gradients and pressure regimes relevant to MSFD assessments.

2.2. Sample collection and laboratory analyses

A total of 290 zooplankton samples were collected during the warm season (May–September) of 2013–2020 at fixed monitoring stations distributed across the three MRUs: T (N = 49), C (N = 112), and M (N = 129) (Table 1).

Vertical hauls covering the entire water column, from the bottom to the surface, were performed using a Juday net (mouth area 0.1 m²; mesh size 150 µm) equipped with a calibrated flowmeter to quantify the volume of water filtered (Alexandrov et al., 2014). The collected samples were preserved immediately in a 4% buffered formaldehyde–seawater solution.

At each station, temperature and salinity were measured in situ using a CTD profiler, and water samples were collected in Niskin bottles and analyzed for dissolved oxygen, phosphate (PO₄³⁻), silicate (SiO₄⁴⁻), nitrite (NO₂⁻), nitrate (NO₃⁻), and ammonium (NH₄⁺) following standard spectrophotometric methods (Mullin and Riley, 1955; Grasshoff et al., 1999). Dissolved oxygen concentrations were determined from discrete seawater samples using the Winkler titration method, involving the chemical fixation of dissolved oxygen and subsequent iodometric titration (Grasshoff et al., 1999). Nitrate concentrations were based on the reduction of nitrate to nitrite using hydrazine sulfate, followed by spectrophotometric determination after diazotization. Ammonium was analyzed using the indophenol blue method, in which ammonia reacts with hypochlorite under alkaline conditions to form a blue-colored compound that is measured spectrophotometrically. Inorganic phosphate was determined by the molybdenum blue method,

whereby phosphate reacts with ammonium molybdate in acidic conditions to form a phosphomolybdenum complex reduced to a blue compound and measured at 885 nm. Dissolved silicate was analyzed using the silicomolybdate method, with reduction by ascorbic acid and spectrophotometric detection at 810 nm (Mullin and Riley, 1955; Grasshoff et al., 1999). All nutrient concentrations were expressed in µM.

In the laboratory, zooplankton samples were gently homogenized, and 2-mL subsamples were withdrawn for analysis. Subsamples were examined in a Bogorov counting chamber under a stereomicroscope. Cladocerans were identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level using standard taxonomic keys (Mordukhay-Boltovskoy, 1968, 1972). Abundance was calculated as density (ind/m³), and biomass (mg/m³) was estimated using the published species-specific standard individual wet-weight values compiled for Black Sea zooplankton (Petipa, 1957). For each taxon, numerical abundance was multiplied by the corresponding standard individual weight to obtain species-specific and total biomass.

2.3. Data analysis

Variability plots were generated to illustrate both temporal (interannual) and spatial (MRU-specific) trends in cladoceran density and biomass, allowing visual assessment of major fluctuations and gradients across the study period. To complement these summaries, shade plots were produced to depict the distribution patterns of cladoceran species, providing an integrated view of density and biomass variability across stations and years. Square-root transformation was applied only to the year- and MRU-based shade plots.

For each taxon and MRU, frequency (%) was computed as the proportion of samples in which the species was present, according to the formula:

$$\text{Frequency (\%)} = \frac{n_{\text{presence}}}{n_{\text{total}}} \times 100,$$

where n_{presence} is the number of samples with non-zero average abundance and biomass for Cladocera species, and n_{total} is the total number of samples in the MRU.

Table 1. Spatial characteristics of zooplankton sampling stations across MRUs in the Romanian Black Sea (2013–2020).

MRU	Number of stations	Number of samples	Station depth range (m)	Latitude range (°N)	Longitude range (°E)	Dominant hydrodynamic setting
Transitional (T)	8	49	5–20	44.68–45.15	29.01–29.79	River-influenced, strong mixing
Coastal (C)	17	112	5–20	43.95–44.98	28.64–29.99	Coastal circulation
Marine (M)	20	129	30–100	44.22–45.00	28.70–30.32	Offshore shelf circulation

Station depth range corresponds to the bottom depth at each sampling station. All zooplankton samples were collected by vertical hauls covering the entire water column.

Mean individual biomass (MIB, $\text{mg}/\text{ind}^{-1}$) was calculated using the formula:

$$MIB = \frac{B}{N}$$

where B is total biomass, and N is total density for each sample, providing an index of cladoceran community size structure (Hirst and Bunker, 2003).

Multivariate differences in cladoceran community composition among MRUs were tested using analysis of similarities (ANOSIM), based on Bray–Curtis resemblance matrices calculated from square-root-transformed abundance data in order to reduce the influence of highly dominant taxa. Statistical significance was assessed using 999 permutations in PRIMER v7 (Clarke, 2014).

Normality was tested using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test in Statistica, which indicated nonnormal distributions ($p < 0.05$). Consequently, nonparametric Spearman rank correlation analyses were applied to examine relationships between environmental variables (temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, PO_4^{3-} , SiO_4^{4-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+) and cladoceran density and biomass, calculated separately for each MRU. Environmental variables were analyzed in their measured units, and correlations were interpreted as exploratory. Correlation matrices were visualized as heatmaps in R, with statistical significance assessed at

$p < 0.05$. No formal correction for multiple testing was applied, and so correlations should be interpreted with caution as exploratory patterns rather than definitive causal relationships.

All analyses were performed using PRIMER v7 (Clarke, 2014) and Statistica version 14.01 (TIBCO Software Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA), while additional visualizations of correlation patterns were produced in R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria, 2023).

3. Results

3.1. Temporal and spatial patterns of cladoceran density and biomass

Cladoceran density exhibited clear interannual variability between 2013 and 2020 (Figure 2). Higher values were recorded in 2015 and 2018, while lower densities occurred in 2014, 2016, 2017, and 2020. Spatially, transitional and coastal waters consistently showed higher densities than the marine MRU.

Cladoceran biomass followed a broadly similar temporal pattern (Figure 2), with a pronounced maximum in 2018 and reduced values in 2014, 2016, 2017, and 2020. Intermediate biomass levels were observed in 2013, 2015, and 2019. As with density, biomass values were consistently higher in transitional and coastal waters than in marine waters.

Figure 2. Variability of cladoceran density (ind/m^3) and biomass (mg/m^3) by year (2013–2020) and MRU.

Mean individual biomass (MIB) also varied markedly across the study period (Figure 3). The lowest MIB values were observed in 2014, 2015, and 2020, whereas higher values occurred in 2016 and 2018. Intermediate MIB values were recorded in 2013, 2017, and 2019. In contrast to density and biomass, MIB tended to be slightly higher in marine waters than in transitional and coastal zones.

3.2. Species composition and dominance patterns

ANOSIM revealed significant differences in cladoceran community composition among MRUs (Global $R = 0.169$, $p = 0.033$). In total, nine cladoceran taxa were identified. *Pleopis polyphemoides* dominated the assemblage, occurring in 100% of samples across all zones, while *Penilia avirostris* also showed consistently high frequencies (62.5% in transitional; 87.5% in coastal; and 71.4% in marine waters); together, these taxa accounted for most of the annual abundance and biomass. *Pseudevadne tergestina* contributed at moderate levels and increased in occurrence from transitional waters (37.5%) to coastal (62.5%) and marine areas (71.4%), reflecting its recurrent presence in warm-season communities. *Evadne spinifera* similarly showed higher frequencies in coastal (75%) and marine waters (71.4%) than in transitional areas (37.5%). In contrast, freshwater–brackish taxa such as *Bosmina longirostris* (37.5%), *Chydorus sphaericus* (12.5%), and *Daphnia longispina* (12.5%) were limited to the transitional zone. *Diaphanosoma brachyurum* was detected only in marine samples (14.3%), while *Podon* spp. was rare and occurred exclusively in the coastal zone (12.5%) (Figure 4).

Shade plot visualizations of abundance and biomass (Figures 5 and 6) revealed a consistent spatial–temporal structuring in the cladoceran community. Transitional and coastal waters clustered closely for both metrics and were characterized by recurrent dominances of *P. polyphemoides* and *P. avirostris* across most years. These

taxa formed high-intensity zones in both shade plots, indicating persistently elevated abundance and biomass in nearshore MRUs.

Marine waters formed a distinct group, exhibiting lower overall abundance and biomass while retaining the same dominant taxa at reduced intensities. Secondary species, including *P. tergestina*, *E. spinifera*, and *Podon* spp., occurred irregularly in isolated low-intensity patches with limited temporal and spatial extent. The remaining taxa appeared only sporadically, accounting for only minor proportions of total abundance and biomass.

3.3. Environmental drivers of cladoceran density and biomass

Environmental parameters exhibited well-defined spatial gradients across the three MRUs. Transitional waters were the coolest (mean 20.9 °C), and were markedly less saline (10.4‰), oxygen-rich (333 µM), and strongly nutrient-enriched—particularly in silicate (mean 24.8 µM, with peaks up to 95.8 µM)—reflecting the substantial influence of the Danube River inputs. Intermediate conditions were noted in the coastal waters, with slightly higher temperatures (21.6 °C), increased salinity (14.5‰), moderate oxygen concentrations (313 µM), and reduced nutrient levels compared with transitional stations (silicate mean 6.2 µM). The marine region exhibited the warmest (22.6 °C) and most saline waters (15.5‰), and had lower oxygen levels (310 µM), and generally low nutrient concentrations (Table 2).

Spearman correlation analyses revealed temperature to be the strongest and most consistent predictor of cladoceran density and biomass across all MRUs, with positive correlations increasing from transitional to marine waters ($\rho = 0.32$ – 0.45). Salinity displayed weaker positive associations, whereas dissolved oxygen and silicate were generally negatively correlated with cladocerans,

Figure 3. Temporal variation in the average mean individual biomass of cladocerans (mg ind^{-1}) across MRUs during 2013–2020.

Figure 4. Frequency of occurrence (%) of cladoceran taxa across MRUs.

Figure 5. Shade plot of average cladoceran density across sampling years (2013–2020) and Marine Reporting Units (T, C, M), illustrating interannual and spatial variation. Data were square-root transformed before analysis and visualized using Bray–Curtis resemblance in PRIMER v7. Darker shading indicates higher density values.

particularly in coastal and marine waters. Nutrient relationships were more spatially variable: in coastal waters, cladoceran density and biomass were positively correlated with nitrite and negatively with ammonium, while both variables showed weak negative associations with phosphate and nitrate in marine waters. Overall, temperature emerged as a main driver of cladoceran variability, while nutrient effects differed across the transitional, coastal, and marine waters (Figure 7).

4. Discussion

4.1. Temporal and spatial variability

Interannual variability emerged as a defining feature of cladoceran dynamics during the study period, highlighting the sensitivity of these communities to year-on-year

changes in environmental conditions. These fluctuations are consistent with the high sensitivity of cladoceran communities to hydroclimatic variability (Richardson, 2008; Üstün et al., 2018; Üstün, 2025; Yildiz, 2025). In the present study, temperature variability showed the most consistent relationships with cladoceran density and biomass across MRUs, providing direct support for its role in shaping interannual patterns. The potential influence of water-column stratification and Danube River discharge is not quantified on an interannual basis, and is therefore inferred from broader regional observations. Warmer conditions during the sampling period, often associated with enhanced and stable stratification, are known to favor cladoceran growth and reproduction, whereas periods characterized by cooler temperatures, increased mixing,

Figure 6. Shade plot of average cladoceran biomass across sampling years (2013–2020) and Marine Reporting Units (T, C, M), illustrating interannual and spatial variation. Data were square-root transformed before analysis and visualized using Bray–Curtis resemblance in PRIMER v7; darker shading indicates higher biomass values.

Table 2. Summary of environmental conditions (mean ± SD and range) across MRUs: T = transitional, C = coastal, M = marine in the Romanian Black Sea during 2013–2020.

Variable	MRU = T (N = 49)	MRU = C (N = 112)	MRU = M (N = 129)
T (°C)	20.9 ± 3.0 (14.9–25.1)	21.6 ± 2.9 (16.1–26.5)	22.6 ± 2.9 (15.3–27.1)
S (‰)	10.4 ± 5.3 (0.2–18.5)	14.5 ± 3.2 (2.7–19.1)	15.5 ± 3.1 (0.1–19.9)
O ₂ (µM)	333 ± 56.7 (253–496)	313 ± 48.2 (214–450)	310 ± 55.3 (119–452)
PO ₄ (µM)	0.59 ± 0.57 (0.02–3.04)	0.35 ± 0.37 (0.01–2.28)	0.24 ± 0.22 (0.01–1.08)
SiO ₄ (µM)	24.8 ± 24.1 (1.2–95.8)	6.2 ± 4.9 (0.5–27.4)	5.8 ± 7.0 (0.05–45.0)
NO ₂ (µM)	2.9 ± 8.0 (0.03–50.9)	2.9 ± 6.1 (0.01–42.3)	1.7 ± 4.5 (0.01–28.0)
NO ₃ (µM)	8.8 ± 9.3 (0.07–52.0)	5.8 ± 9.2 (0.01–69.2)	4.2 ± 6.8 (0.01–56.3)
NH ₄ (µM)	7.9 ± 8.5 (0.43–38.1)	8.1 ± 7.8 (0.12–38.5)	8.7 ± 8.1 (0.38–53.6)
DIN (µM)	19.6 ± 16.5 (1.7–104.1)	16.8 ± 13.8 (1.6–91.2)	14.6 ± 12.0 (1.6–69.2)

DIN (dissolved inorganic nitrogen), calculated as the sum of nitrite (NO₂⁻), nitrate (NO₃⁻), and ammonium (NH₄⁺) concentrations (DIN = NO₂⁻ + NO₃⁻ + NH₄⁺).

or reduced primary production tend to constrain their development (Adamczuk, 2024; Shiganova and Kazmin, 2024; Yildiz, 2025). Comparable oscillations in cladoceran phenology and abundance have been reported in other temperate and semi-enclosed marine systems, where hydroclimatic forcing is recognized as an important background driver of zooplankton variability (Killi, 2020; He et al., 2023; Gyulai et al., 2024).

The differences observed between transitional and coastal cladoceran communities are consistent with patterns reported for other river-influenced and semi-enclosed coastal ecosystems, where strong gradients in salinity, nutrient availability, and hydrodynamic conditions structure zooplankton assemblages (Oguz and Velikova, 2010; Lazar et al., 2024; Ristea et al., 2025).

Transitional zones are typically characterized by high variability driven by episodic freshwater inputs and nutrient enrichment, whereas coastal waters often support more stable assemblages dominated by a limited number of euryhaline and marine taxa. Similar spatial structuring of cladoceran communities has been documented in the Baltic Sea, Mediterranean coastal lagoons, and temperate estuarine systems, where river-sea interactions and stratification dynamics regulate the species composition, phenology, and functional roles of cladocerans (Green et al., 2005; Havel, 2009; Souza et al., 2011; Killi, 2020; Adamczuk, 2024; Yildiz, 2025). The convergences between the findings of these studies and those of the present study suggest that the transitional-coastal contrasts observed in the Romanian Black Sea reflect the general ecological

Figure 7. Heatmap of Spearman rank correlation coefficients (ρ) between environmental parameters and cladoceran density and biomass across MRUs (T, C, M). Color intensity reflects the strength and direction of correlations (see scale). * indicates statistically significant correlations at $p < 0.05$.

responses of cladocerans to river-influenced coastal environments rather than site-specific processes.

A particularly relevant regional comparison is supported by the 5-year monthly study conducted in the semi-enclosed Sea of Marmara (Bedikoğlu et al., 2022)—a stratified and seasonally productive basin influenced by Black Sea surface outflow and characterized by hydrographic variability (Yalçın et al., 2017). Pronounced interannual shifts in zooplankton abundance and species dominance, including fluctuations in *P. avirostris*, have also been reported (Bedikoğlu et al., 2022). These patterns mirror the variability observed in the present study, in which temperature and spatial differences among MRUs are linked to changes in cladoceran density, biomass, and dominance structure. The agreement between the two systems suggests that hydroenvironmental forcing and stratification act as common structuring mechanisms in Black Sea-connected basins, indicating that the patterns observed along the Romanian coast reflect broader regional processes rather than site-specific dynamics.

4.2. Variability in cladoceran size structure

Transitional and coastal waters consistently support higher densities and biomasses than marine areas, indicating

enhanced nutrient availability, elevated phytoplankton production, and intensified secondary productivity driven by Danube inputs and nearshore mixing (Moncheva et al., 2001; Svetlichny et al., 2006; Cociasu et al., 2009). Although the marine zone was generally less productive, increased mean individual biomass was sometimes noted, indicating a greater prevalence of larger-bodied cladocerans under conditions of reduced competition, lower grazing pressure, or a more stable hydrographic structure.

The observed alternation between small- and large-bodied dominance underscores the shifts in community size structure—a key functional property that shapes the grazing efficiency, trophic transfer, and strength of energy pathways from zooplankton to planktivorous fish (Llope et al., 2011; Bişinicu et al., 2024; Bisinicu and Harcota, 2025). Such size-structure dynamics reflect the combined effects of resource availability, predation, and environmental forcing, and provide valuable insights into the functioning and resilience of the Black Sea pelagic food web. Similar functional implications of size-structure variability have also been discussed for the Marmara system, reinforcing the role of hydrographic forcing in the regulation of trophic pathways in semi-enclosed Black Sea-connected

basins (Bedikoğlu et al., 2022). Potential links between the observed cladoceran dynamics and pelagic fish production are discussed here as hypotheses, based on the trophic relationships reported in previous Black Sea studies. As no fish abundance, feeding, or diet data were analyzed in the present study, these relationships should be regarded as extrapolations from earlier research rather than as direct evidence derived from the current dataset (Daskalov, 2003; Llope et al., 2011; Bişinicu et al., 2024).

4.3. Species composition and dominance

The spatial and temporal patterns observed in the cladoceran community are characterized by a strong dominance of marine specialist taxa and only sporadic incursions of freshwater-brackish species. *P. polyphemoides* and *P. avirostris*, both well adapted to the warm, low-salinity marine conditions (Pöllupüü et al., 2010; Kodama et al., 2021; Üstün et al., 2026) that are typical of the western Black Sea, consistently dominated across all zones, confirming their role as core components of the regional zooplankton community (Kovalev et al., 2001; Anninsky et al., 2025). The moderate but recurrent presence of *P. tergestina* and *E. spinifera* further emphasizes the importance of warm-season cladocerans that respond rapidly to favorable stratification and elevated temperatures (Miyashita et al., 2011; Gubanova et al., 2022).

A comparable dominance pattern has been reported for the semienclosed Sea of Marmara, where *P. avirostris* and *P. polyphemoides* are the most abundant cladocerans (Bedikoğlu et al., 2022). In the Sea of Marmara, populations are dominated (60–100%) by parthenogenetic females, ensuring rapid reproduction and increased embryo production even during population declines, indicating strong reproductive plasticity under variable hydrographic conditions. The persistent dominance of *Pleopis* and *Penilia* across MRUs in the present study is consistent with this finding, suggesting that rapid parthenogenetic responses to temperature and stratification help sustain cladoceran dominance in Black Sea-connected basins (Bedikoğlu et al., 2022).

In contrast, freshwater-brackish taxa such as *B. longirostris*, *C. sphaericus*, and *D. longispina* were restricted to transitional waters in the present study, reflecting their limited salinity tolerance and the strong influence of lagoonal systems and Danube outflows in these areas (Gutkowska et al., 2018; Adamczuk and Mieczan, 2019). Their absence in coastal and marine stations indicates that these species cannot persist once salinity exceeds their physiological range. The rare detection of *D. brachyurum* in marine samples is ecologically unusual, but most likely reflects episodic transport from nearby lagoonal systems, coupled with transient low-salinity microhabitats in the Portița area (Giosan et al., 2005; Bisinicu et al., 2023). Similarly, the sporadic occurrence of *Podon* spp. suggests that these taxa remain minor contributors and exert limited

influence on the overall community structure. Overall, the assemblage is strongly skewed toward a few dominant marine cladocerans, with most other species appearing only occasionally as transient or advected components.

Shade plot visualizations reinforced these patterns, showing higher similarity between transitional and coastal zones driven by the persistent dominance of *Pleopis* and *Penilia*. Although marine waters supported lower total abundances, they retained the same core species, indicating that the fundamental cladoceran community composition remains stable across the nearshore-offshore gradient. Similar dominance structures have been documented in previous studies from the Black Sea, the Sea of Marmara and other regional coastal systems, highlighting the persistent and regionally characteristic nature of warm-season cladoceran assemblages (Bedikoğlu et al., 2022; Shiganova and Kazmin, 2024; Anninsky et al., 2025; Üstün, 2025).

The use of a Juday net with a 150 µm mesh size may have led to an underestimation of the smallest cladoceran taxa and early developmental stages, as finer meshes (e.g., 100 µm) are known to retain small-bodied individuals more efficiently. However, the selected mesh size follows long-term Black Sea zooplankton monitoring protocols, ensuring consistency and comparability with historical regional datasets (Alexandrov et al., 2014). As a result, the observed patterns primarily reflect variability in the dominant and most ecologically relevant cladoceran taxa.

4.4. Environmental drivers

Environmental gradients across the three MRUs provide essential context for interpretation of cladoceran community patterns. The strong riverine influence in transitional waters promotes dynamic conditions that favor episodic freshwater-brackish taxa and enhanced short-term productivity, as widely reported for the northwestern Black Sea (Yuney et al., 2002; Cociasu et al., 2009). In coastal waters, intermediate salinity and nutrient levels supported relatively stable assemblages dominated by the euryhaline marine cladocerans *P. polyphemoides* and *P. avirostris*. In contrast, offshore marine conditions were associated with lower total cladoceran density and biomass, while retaining the same core species, suggesting adaptation to more oligotrophic and hydrographically stable environments (Richardson, 2008; Shiganova and Kazmin, 2024). These gradients likely shape cladoceran communities indirectly by influencing food availability, stratification, and habitat stability, thereby reinforcing the observed spatial differentiation among MRUs.

Temperature emerged as the most consistent predictor of cladoceran variability across the MRUs, highlighting their physiological sensitivity and the dominant role of hydroclimatic forcing in regulating warm-season zooplankton dynamics. Nutrient influences were more

spatially heterogeneous: in transitional waters, nutrient-cladoceran correlations were generally weak, whereas in coastal waters, cladoceran density and biomass were positively associated with nitrite and negatively correlated with ammonium, reflecting the strong influence of riverine inputs and nearshore biogeochemical gradients (Moncheva et al., 2001). In marine waters, cladocerans showed weak negative associations with phosphate and nitrate, consistent with the nutrient limitations in offshore, oligotrophic shelf environments (Oguz and Velikova, 2010). These contrasting relationships demonstrate that cladoceran dynamics are shaped by a combination of hydrographic gradients and nutrient availability.

Projected warming and shifts in Danube discharge are likely to intensify variability in Black Sea cladoceran communities (Gericke and Venohr, 2021; Lazar et al., 2022; Lazar et al., 2024a; Lazar et al., 2024b). Increasing temperatures may promote the dominance of small-bodied cladocerans with lower grazing efficiency, while altered nutrient deliveries linked to changing river outflows could trigger episodic increases in opportunistic or fast-growing taxa (Razlutskiy et al., 2018; Uszko et al., 2022). Together, these changes have the potential to restructure zooplankton-fish interactions by modifying prey availability, size structure, and seasonal timing, with cascading effects on fish recruitment success and overall ecosystem productivity (Heneghan et al., 2023; Ratnarajah et al., 2023). Such responses are consistent with the broader climate-driven restructuring observed in other semi-enclosed marine systems, highlighting the Black Sea's sensitivity to simultaneous warming and hydrological change (Richardson, 2008; Adamczuk, 2024; Ristea et al., 2025).

4.5. Ecological and management implications

Cladocerans occupy a central position in the Black Sea pelagic food web, functioning both as efficient grazers of phytoplankton and as key prey for planktivorous fish, thereby facilitating energy transfer to higher trophic levels (Bişinicu et al., 2024). Their fluctuations, shifts in size structure, and strong sensitivity to hydroclimatic variability reinforce their value as responsive indicators of ecosystem change (Daskalov, 2003; Llope et al., 2011). The persistent dominance of *P. polyphemoides* and *P. avirostris* across MRUs reflects the stability of a core warm-season community, while the episodic occurrence of secondary taxa highlights potential vulnerabilities to environmental extremes and altered hydrographic regimes.

Within the MSFD, the integration of cladoceran-based metrics—such as density, biomass, and mean individual biomass—into Descriptor 4 (Food Webs) would complement existing copepod-focused indicators. Incorporating these metrics could enhance the sensitivity and ecological relevance of Good Environmental Status

assessments by capturing further dimensions of pelagic food-web functioning. Such an approach would align Black Sea monitoring efforts with the ecosystem-based management practices implemented in other European regional seas (Borja et al., 2016; Uusitalo et al., 2016).

5. Conclusion

The present study provides new insights into the spatial and interannual dynamics of cladoceran communities in the Romanian sector of the Black Sea, specifically by resolving patterns across the transitional-coastal-marine gradient during the warm season.

A key finding of the study is that cladoceran assemblages are consistently structured around a small number of dominant marine taxa, while the majority of species occur sporadically and contribute marginally to overall abundance and biomass.

The main novelty of this work lies in its integrated use of abundance, biomass, and size-structure indicators for the assessment of functional variability in cladoceran communities. Shifts in mean individual biomass and alternations between small- and large-bodied dominance capture changes in community size structure that are not evident from taxonomic composition alone. These size-based patterns provide ecologically meaningful information related to grazing dynamics and trophic transfer, highlighting the added value of functional indicators in zooplankton monitoring.

Although temperature emerged as the most consistent environmental correlate of cladoceran variability, the moderate strength of the observed relationships indicates that cladoceran dynamics are governed by multiple interacting drivers rather than a single dominant factor. By combining spatially explicit analyses with functional metrics, this study strengthens the role of cladocerans as sensitive indicators of environmental variability and supports their application in ecosystem-based assessment and monitoring of the Black Sea, including within the framework of the MSFD.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: EB, LL; Methodology: EB, LL; Investigation: EB, LL; Data analysis: EB; Writing—original draft: EB; Writing—review and editing: LL; Supervision and funding acquisition: EB.

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